

An Assessment of Research and Innovation Hubs in Teachers' Colleges in Zimbabwe: Teacher Education in Alignment with Education 5.0

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This study evaluated Research and Innovation Hubs (RIHubs) conceptualisation, availability and impact in teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe, in the era of e-learning, and the context of aligning with the demands of the Heritage-Based Education 5.0 (HBE 5.0) policy. There were noticeable gaps in lack of institutional research culture, human capital resource incapacity, sustainability challenges, including inadequate budgetary support, and limited infrastructure and technology, despite an enabling policy framework and operating environment. This study sought to establish how RIHubs are understood in TE and how they have impacted the expectations of the HBE 5.0 policy in Higher and Tertiary Education Institutions (HTEIs), in Zimbabwe. This research study sought to enhance perspectives on research, innovation, RIHubs, and industrialisation for sustainable development. It also sought to add to the literature on Teacher Education (TE) alignment with national socio-economic strategies and policies like the Zimbabwe's National Development Strategy 1 (NDS1) and HBE 5,0 respectively. The Constructive Alignment Theory (CAT) and the Unified Progression Model (UPM) guided this qualitative study that employed the embedded multiple case study method. The study found that there is a need for teachers' colleges to upscale the development and utilisation of RIHubs by addressing various challenges that are an impediment to their full establishment and effective exploitation. This study recommended the PFETE framework for research and innovation in TE, which was developed by the author. It can be argued that the construction and effective utilisation of RIHubs in TE is key to the realisation of HBE 5.0 philosophy, NDS1 & 2 and subsequently, sustainable socio-economic development in Zimbabwe.

Keywords: Education 5.0, innovation, research, research and innovation hubs, teacher education

In a comparative analysis of innovation hubs in London and Lusaka conducted at the University of Sheffield, Jimenez and Zheng (2021) noted that RIHubs were quickly spreading over the globe. They praised RIHubs as coworking spaces that foster entrepreneurship, creativity, and teamwork. They pointed out that, as part of a worldwide phenomena, it is important to acknowledge the diversity of spaces and to be sensitive to the politics of lived disparities between the "celebrated imaginary" and "the performed local

practices." As varied as RIHubs are throughout the world, they are unavoidably plagued by a number of issues that limit their efficacy. Nevertheless, RIHubs were found capable of addressing various challenges faced by many nations.

Khoury et al. (2024) in a study on research and innovation, conducted in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), observed that Innovation hubs led by HEIs would help a country address certain challenges shown in Table 1.

Table 1: *Challenges that can be Addressed by RIHubs in HEIs*

1. Funding allocation - inefficient allocation of funding in research, development, and innovation (RDI) areas
2. Research, development, and innovation - insufficient channelling of global trends and national ambitions into focused RDI efforts in priority sectors and fields to drive innovation levels and socioeconomic development (either directly through increased investments and added jobs, or indirectly through spillover effects into the economy)
3. Integration of academic research with industry - lack of adequate partnerships between industry and academia to translate core research into market-Ready products
4. Talent development - insufficient levels of top talent (e.g., students and researchers) and inadequate upskilling of existing talent in labour force
5. Culture and mindset - legacy mindset in academia within HEIs focused on traditional learning and lacking adequate risk-taking culture

Note. Source: Khoury et al. (2024)

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According to a study by Singh and Shakir (2019), lack of professional development, lack of training in ICT, inadequate focus on research and innovations, and infrastructural constraints were some of the challenges faced by teacher education RIHubs in India (Dange & Siddaraju, 2020).

Despite the challenges faced by RIHubs in India, some success stories have been recorded elsewhere. In a study on University Integrated Hubs, using Kenyatta University, Nyiringago (2024) observed that appropriate university resources, high quality education and collaboration significantly contributed to the success of Chandria Centre for Innovation in Kenya. Similarly, this study sought to interrogate RIHubs establishment and utilisation challenges and opportunities, in teachers' colleges, to advance the HBE 5.0 curriculum and indeed sustainable socio-economic development in Zimbabwe.

In Zimbabwe, the HBE 5.0 policy framework has ushered in a new era in TE with new demands for methodologies that are student-centred, interactive, practical-oriented, research and innovation-guided, and technology-based (Maposa & Maposa, 2020; Chigora & Zvavahera, 2022). Zishiri, Jekese and Muchabaiwa (2024; 117) observed that, "Without adequate technological resources, institutions were struggling to incorporate innovative teaching methods, personalised learning experiences and interactive digital platforms which are fundamental aspects of Education 5.0." Such methodologies are ideal in RIHubs. Research, innovation and industrialisation emerged as key components of the HBE 5.0 practice, thereby bringing about the need for RIHubs and Industrial Parks. A quick survey and needs analysis of TE in Zimbabwe, in the context of HBE 5.0, showed that teacher colleges lagged behind in establishing and utilising RIHubs. Makota, Mapolisa, and Munzara (2024) argued that there was a lack of relevant and appropriate ICT culture in teacher education in Zimbabwe, contrary to the new HBE 5.0 policy guidelines. It was observed, in this study, that these colleges faced various challenges in trying to establish, let alone effectively utilise, RIHubs.

Review of Literature

Theoretical Framework

The Constructive Alignment Theory: Biggs (2014) used the Constructive Alignment Theory (CAT) as an example of an outcome-based education (OBE) framework. According to Adusei (2016), John Biggs invented the CAT, which is based on constructivism and curricular theory. According to Adusei (2016), Biggs, and Tang (2011), the CAT reflects the marriage of a constructivist view of learning and an aligned instructional design. The CAT is an outcomes-based strategy that defines student-centered learning outcomes before teaching begins (Biggs & Tang, 2011). CAT focusses on what and how students learn, rather than the lecturer's substance or themes. The CAT, with its emphasis on outcome-based teaching and learning, is consistent with Zimbabwe's HBE 5.0 curriculum and can thus help to improve research and innovation pedagogy in HTEIs. Using the CAT to construct RIHubs in HTEIs would significantly improve long-term socioeconomic growth. "Constructive alignment offers a different approach for curriculum developers, enabling educators to consider the end product (outcomes) and then form teaching, learning and assessment activities which match" (Joseph & Juwah, 2011; 2). This study contends that the constructive alignment method, with its emphasis

on intended student outcomes that define what and how students learn, could assist address some emerging RIHub development and utilisation challenges, as well as TE gaps.

The Unified Progression Model (UPM): The UPM framework is based on four progression models created by Gibb (2008), Benker et al. (2011), Rusmussen and Nybje (2013), and Lackeus (2013). This model was chosen for this investigation because of its general characteristics and similarity to the HBE framework. Lackeus (2015) highlighted generic aspects shared by all four progression models he utilised to create the UPM, including a team-based approach, an emphasis on value creation, linking to the outside world, and allowing learners to apply their knowledge and abilities. This study identified these features as crucial because they are similar to the HBE 5.0 policy features of research, community participation, value generation, innovation, industrialisation, and sustainable development.

This study on RIH in TE benefited from the UPM because it is targeted towards people creating new kinds of value in all areas of society and all walks of life (Lackeus, 2015). Value Creation Pedagogy is key to the HBE 5.0 policy, making the UPM paradigm applicable and relevant for this study on RIHubs in teachers' colleges. The VaCP adheres to constructivist concepts, allowing students to create their own learning and meaning (Mueller and Anderson, 2014; Bell, 2020). HBE 5.0 emphasises value creation in addition to venture development by establishing and using RIHubs, allowing students to learn by applying their knowledge to produce value for external stakeholders (Lackeus et al., 2016; Bell, 2020).

However, the UPM had certain flaws in this study, such as their notion that EE should begin at a young age, which did not align with the study's goal. This study hypothesised that treatments implemented at the tertiary level would have an equal impact. Nonetheless, this analysis showed the UPM to be extremely helpful, despite the fact that minimal emphasis was placed on previous education levels declared important by the UPM but deemed out of scope for this study.

Programmatic Framework for Research-based, Innovative and Entrepreneurial Teacher Education (PFRIETE): A theoretical framework is a structure that the researcher believes will best describe the natural course of the topic under study (Camp, 2001). It can be pictorial or narrative, and it depicts the relationship between the study's primary concepts and the sequence of actions the researcher wants to do (Adom, Agyem, & Hussein, 2018). Theoretical frameworks provide numerous benefits to research. They help people recognise and create their own worldviews about the subject under study (Grant & Osanloo, 2014). The proposed theoretical framework for this study is the approved Programmatic Framework for Research-Based, Innovative, and Entrepreneurial Teacher Education (PFRIETE). This framework's major themes included research, innovation, and entrepreneurial education, which encompassed value creation, as well as Heritage-based Education 5.0. The PFRIETE, like Lakeus' (2015) approach, consists of three phases, which correspond to three years of pre-service teacher education.

In this proposed conceptual framework, industrialisation and massification should be considered as cross-cutting topics in all TE curriculum disciplines. However, Research and Innovation should take the lead in meeting the majority of student teachers' entrepreneurial demands. In addition to aiming for skill-based value

creation, entrepreneurship is anticipated to spearhead and strengthen long-term venture creation and massification.

In the first year, students confront societal difficulties and everyday problems based on their own interests and ideas, which are integrated into fundamental courses of the TE curriculum and cross-cutting themes of industrialisation and massification. According to Lakeus (2015), active participation among students promotes creativity, engagement, self-efficacy, and uncertainty and ambiguity. TE continues the embedded approach in the second year, but with a greater emphasis on applying curriculum knowledge, which should involve significant research and innovation that integrates indigenous knowledge systems and entrepreneurship, according to the HTE 5.0 policy framework (Garwe, 2018; Maphosa & Maphosa, 2020; Chigora & Zvavahera, 2022). Integrated Learning should empower students to produce goods and services for their local communities.

According to Lackeus (2015), the ideal third-year curriculum for an education diploma would emphasize applying theory, enhancing creative skills, and promoting sustainable ventures. The goal is to develop a patriotic, entrepreneurial teacher with strong research and innovation capabilities, thereby preparing the workforce needed to achieve socio-economic development through industrialization.

RIHubs Literature Review

RIHub Concept in Teacher Education: The emergence of innovation hubs (as coworking spaces) in the Global North is situated within a context of a shifting knowledge economy, where ideals of creativity and innovation are intimately tied to conditions of flexibility, precarity, mobility, and self-enterprise (Ivaldi, Pais, & Scaratti, 2018; Parrino, 2015; Spinuzzi, 2012; Jimenez & Zheng, 2021). According to Simuka and Chinakidzwa (2022: 158), “the concept of innovation hubs is defined as a centre of research and development of innovative ideas that support and create an enabling environment for budding entrepreneurs at different growth stages.”

RIHubs in TE advance collaboration, knowledge development, research, innovation and entrepreneurship to improve teaching/learning practices and practical application of research findings to improve teaching/learning processes and student outcomes. Afrilab and Briter Bridges (2019) define a RIHub as a centre for learning, ideas, cocreation, and community that fosters innovative ideas and market disruption while also supporting creative problem-solving approaches by providing on-the-ground support throughout the startup lifecycle. RIHubs enable student instructors, educators, and researchers to interact, share ideas, and discover innovative solutions to educational and community concerns (MHTEISTD, 2018).

The Place of RIHubs in Heritage-based Teacher Education: RIHubs in teachers' colleges play a pivotal role in enhancing quality of the heritage-based teacher education through fostering innovation and entrepreneurship, community engagement, and improved student outcomes. They also contribute to improved and effective education systems as well as enhance the socio-economic development of the nation as a whole.

The University of Zimbabwe (2024;4) published.

The Framework for Quality Assurance in Associate Teacher Education Colleges and Polytechnics ... (which) is alive to the dictates of Zimbabwe Vision 2030, National Development Strategy 1 (2021-2025), Heritage-based Education 5.0

philosophy, Manpower Planning and Development Act (Chapter 28:02) and the University of Zimbabwe Strategic Plan (2019-2025).

The framework places more emphasis on research, as evidenced by the guidelines for Associate Colleges in Table 2. The framework creates a suitable environment for RIHubs to thrive in teachers' colleges. However, one wonders if these institutions are fully exploiting these opportunities.

Table 2

Research Guidelines for UZ Associate Colleges in Zimbabwe

Research

1. Each college should have a research unit.
2. There must be a College Research Guide that is Education 5.0 compliant.
3. Research Guide can be published.
4. The CTMD funds one research workshop per college per year.
However, the college can organise more self-funded workshops as per need.

Note. Source: University of Zimbabwe (2024; 17).

The assumption here is that each college would need more than one research workshop per year and should therefore mobilise adequate financial and manpower resources for the additional workshops to happen.

Enhancing the HBTE 5.0 through Fostering Research, Innovation and Entrepreneurship: RIHubs inform and enhance teacher education programmes in that they ensure that lecturers and student teachers are equipped with research-based practices and innovative approaches to teaching and learning. Teacher education must incorporate inquiry and research skills that prepare student teachers to be lifelong learners and educators capable of adapting their practice to changing situations and meeting their students' changing needs (Vargas, 2022). RIHubs are the greatest places to fulfil students' shifting demands. RIHubs provide platforms for lecturers and students to develop innovative solutions to educational challenges promoting entrepreneurship and creativity through Interdisciplinary research (MHTEISTD, 2018). Interdisciplinary research can be enhanced through conducting research that combines multiple disciplines, such as history, anthropology, and education, for students to better understand the complexities of heritage-based education (Garwe, 2018; Maphosa & Maphosa, 2020).

HBTE 5.0 requires RIHubs that are useful in fostering community engagement through collaboration with local communities to develop educational programs that promote cultural awareness, understanding, and appreciation (Garwe, 2018; Maphosa & Maphosa, 2020; Chigora & Zvavahera, 2022). In China, “The participation of community members, including cultural practitioners, historians, and artists, in the educational process plays a crucial role in connecting academic learning with authentic cultural experiences (Vargas, 2022). Heron and Wolfe (2021) propose that partnerships between university innovation hubs and schools cover a need in programming aimed at building practical skills linked to the digital transformation of learning settings.

Digital heritage preservation is also achieved through utilisation of technologies that promote cultural values and RIHubs would make them even more accessible to a wider audience. RIHubs are renowned for modern technology utilisation in their programs and

processes. They also preserve cultural heritage by studying, documenting, and promoting it through research, innovation and industrialisation and ensuring its transmission to future generations (Garwe, 2018; Chigora & Zvavahera, 2022). Transmission to future generations is also enhanced through RIHubs in that they provide policy makers and practitioners with relevant, timely and actionable research findings, informing evidence-based policy and practice for the youths.

Informing Ideal Teacher Education Policy and Practice: Ideal research and innovation policy development should inform the TE curriculum worldwide. Well-informed policy development and decision-making at local, national, and international levels, and ensuring that heritage-based education is integrated into educational policies and programs would go a long way in enhancing TE. In a research on university integrated hubs in Kenya, Nyiringago (2024) advised that the government and all other stakeholders should fast speed up the design of national intellectual property legislation.

National policy on intellectual property should incorporate local heritage through relevant curricular. Developing contextualized curriculum through creating content and context that incorporate local heritage would make education more relevant and engaging for students. Heritage-Based STEM Education is consolidated by RIHubs through the development of educational programs that incorporate heritage-based approaches to STEM subjects, thereby making them more engaging and relevant to students' lives. Zimbabwe's HBE 5.0 TE Curriculum demands content and participatory methodologies that are relevant and engaging for student teachers. RIHubs promote teacher professional development by providing student teachers with training, resources, and support to enhance effective integration of heritage-based education into their practice. RIHubs provide a platform for developing and testing innovative teaching methods and technologies that incorporate heritage-based education, and this would enhance student learning outcomes.

RIHubs and the Enhancement of Student Outcomes: Research and innovation hubs can significantly enhance student outcomes in several ways:

- *Enhanced Learning Experiences:* Hands-on learning experience is provided by RIHubs. Students engage in experiential learning, working on real-world projects, and developing practical skills (MHTEISTD, 2018). RIHubs promote interdisciplinary approaches. They foster collaboration across disciplines, exposing students to diverse perspectives and methodologies. They also promote access to cutting-edge technology, whereby student teachers learn to leverage innovative tools, equipment, and software, thereby preparing them for the modern 21st century business environment (Garwe, 2018; Chigora & Zvavahera, 2022; Maphosa & Maphosa, 2020).
- *Improved Academic Performance:* RIHubs create research opportunities for student teachers. They participate in research projects, during which they develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills (MHTEISTD, 2018). Mentorship and guidance are provided by professionals as students carry out these research projects. RIHubs provide students with access to experienced researchers, industry experts, and mentors, offering valuable guidance and support. Such collaborative learning environments provide student teachers with a sense of community engagement, encourage peer teaching, and promote a growth-minded mindset in them (MHTEISTD, 2018).
- *Enhanced Employability and Career Prospect:* RIHubs enhance community engagement and college-industry connection by establishing partnerships with business leaders, providing students with networking opportunities, internships, and job placements (MHTEISTD, 2018). RIH also enhances the development of transferable skills, whereby students develop skills such as communication, teamwork, and project management, thereby making them more attractive to employers. Students also get exposure to emerging trends and technologies through RIHubs. One may conclude, therefore, that RIHubs keep students informed about the latest developments in their field and prepare them for the challenges of a rapidly changing work environment (MHTEISTD, 2018).
- *Increased Entrepreneurial Spirit and Innovations:* Cultivation of an entrepreneurial mindset is enhanced by RIHubs. They encourage students to think creatively, take calculated risks, and develop a growth mindset. RIHubs promote project incubation and acceleration of business programs. In their study to identify the reality of Business Incubations (BIs) and their role in supporting entrepreneurship in HEIs, Rifai et al. (2023) suggested that HEIs must focus on all BIs that may contribute to their success, including administrative, financial, and marketing issues. They also suggested that entrepreneurial courses be made mandatory in higher education institutions. RIHubs offer resources and support for students to develop and launch their own start-ups and innovative projects. Ayatse et al. (2017) observed that incubation is a powerful instrument in the entrepreneurial ecosystem that must be encouraged and supported, as a framework for business support and the proliferation of new ventures.

Access to funding and investment opportunities is improved by RIHubs. They connect students with potential investors, grants, and funding sources, helping to turn their ideas into reality. Initiatives and opportunities created by organisations like the African Export-Import Bank (Afreximbank) are quite commendable. Afrximbank (2025:1), in collaboration with African Union Commission and AfCFTA Secretariat, is launching the “African Research and Innovation Hub @IATF”, during the 4th Intra-African Trade Fair (IATF2025) avowed:

The platform aims to provide an opportunity for African, Caribbean and Diaspora lecturers, students, and researchers to showcase innovative research and prototypes that contribute towards intra-African trade and industrialisation. It also seeks to develop industry collaborations and exchange knowledge with leading professionals in the field during IATF2025 in Algiers, Algeria, from September 4-10, 2025.

Table 3

Success of the Innovation Ecosystem in Kenya

Factors contributing to the success of the innovation ecosystem in Kenya are:

- i. Collaboration between the corporate sector and scientific researchers.
- ii. Infrastructure and inexpensive internet access
- iii. The IHub concept originated in Kenya.
- iv. Kenya is among the top four African countries with the highest innovation ranking, owing to affordable mobile phone service.

Note. Source: Nyiringago (2024).

Improved Student Teacher Community Engagement and Participation in Cultural and Business Exchange Programs: RIHs provide relevant and meaningful learning experiences for student teachers. They provide student teachers with authentic, real-world learning opportunities while increasing their motivation and engagement. The sense of community and belonging amongst student teachers is enhanced by RIHs. RIHs promote community engagement and cultural exchange programs that allow facilitators and students to experience different cultural heritages, thereby promoting cross-cultural understanding and appreciation. Building partnerships and collaborations is also enhanced by RIHs. Chigora and Zvavahera (2022) observed that RIHs foster a sense of community by helping students connect with peers and mentors. In that way, student teachers also feel supported throughout their academic journey.

RIHs provide opportunities for student recognition and celebration. Maphosa and Maphosa, (2020) noted that, RIHs recognize and celebrate student teacher achievements, thereby providing a sense of accomplishment and reinforcing positive behaviours in them. They develop high self-esteem and engage in research and innovation with confidence. They become capable of executing their duties with the tenacity of purpose and the purpose of tenacity, in cultural and business exchange programmes (MHTEISTD, 2018).

Methods of Students Participation: Participatory approaches for youth, such as public workshops, surveys, and digitally-enhanced cultural campaigns, have been tailored to align with student motivations and characteristics (Deitz et al., 2018; Poplin, de Andrade, & de Sena, 2022). Within heritage practices, these methods are classified into three interdependent pathways, awareness-raising, capacity-building, and empowerment, that may be iteratively integrated to deepen youth engagement (Zhang et al., 2024; see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Levels and Methods of Youth Participation

Note. Source: Zhang et al. (2024)

Method

The preceding section of this paper detailed a review of relevant literature. This section discusses the methods used in this study on RIHubs in TE in Zimbabwe.

The Constructivism ideology, the Qualitative approach, the Constructivist-interpretivist paradigm, and the case study method with embedded multiple case design were used in this study on RIHubs at Zimbabwean higher education institutions. To improve

the validity of research findings, this study used the embedded multiple case study approach, which allows researchers to analyse institutions located in diverse case destinations (Wigger, 2018). Given the humanistic nature of the topics under consideration, this study was developed as an embedded, multiple case study with a naturalistic perspective, as evidenced by the social constructivism philosophy used.

Lev Vygotsky founded the idea of social constructivism (1978). The ideas of constructivism state that personal knowledge is socially created rather than innate (McLeod, 2019). The constructivist-interpretivist paradigm holds that numerous, socially constructed realities and contextual elements must be considered in any systematic quest for understanding (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017; Makota et al., 2023). Consequently, this research into RIHubs in TE was guided by the view that knowledge is not singularly discovered but is socially built through personal and plural perspectives. This interpretivist approach values context and the interrelationship between cause and effect (Morgan, 2007; Makota et al., 2024). The study was grounded in the specific realities of Zimbabwe's entrepreneurship education, teacher education, HTE 5.0 policy, and socio-economic development ambitions.

Four data production approaches were used in this study to allow for triangulation and improve the validity of the research findings. These included a focus group discussion (FGD), qualitative document analysis (QDA), key and other informant interviews (K&OI), and observations (OBS). The focus group discussions (SFGDs) included both students and lecturers. The technique used in this study improved the reliability, credibility, transferability, and confirmability of the research findings.

The following section details the findings through data presentation, analysis, and interpretation.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

The Concept and Context of RIHubs in TE

The review of related literature (RRL) has it that RIHubs in teacher education foster collaboration, knowledge development, and practical application of research findings to improve teaching practices and student outcomes. The RRL further noted that RIHubs provide a space for student teachers, educators, researchers, and other stakeholders to connect, share ideas, and develop innovative solutions to address various challenges in education and society at large.

Access and Utilisation of RIHubs in HEIs

From the LFGD, access and utilisation of RIHubs in HEIs, particularly teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe, was observed to be a cause for concern. Respondent: KI1 in Case C, *bemoaned the scarcity of RIHubs in teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe, arguing that what some institutions regarded as innovation hubs were mere ill-equipped computer rooms which were very much limited.* However, KI1 in Case B, reported that, *"We have since established our own research and innovation hub, with relevant ICT equipment."* The differences in the opinions by respondents only highlighted the existence of a knowledge gap around RIHubs in teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe.

Respondent: **KI2 in Case A** raised concern about the knowledge gap, arguing that *teachers' colleges didn't have the qualified personnel to guide the establishment and development of*

RIHubs and their utilisation as teaching/learning centres. They highlighted the need for in-service training to capacitate the lecturers in these HEIs. It was suggested that, perhaps, these lecturers needed to be attached to local or international universities with vibrant research and innovation hubs, in the context of on-the-job training, continuous staff development and professional growth. From the three teachers' colleges observed, none of them seemed to have a RIHub comparable to what is emerging in universities, the LFGD observed. As a result, it is possible to infer that the establishment, access, and use of RIHubs in Zimbabwean teacher colleges remains a significant need that must be addressed if TE is to be effectively linked with the HBE 5.0 policy framework. Perhaps, the answer is in TE preparing pre-service student teachers and in-service teachers in developing and utilising RIHubs as mandatory teaching and learning centres in all educational institutions.

RIHubs in Teacher Preparation and Professional Growth

The SFGD concluded that given the need for RIHubs in HEIs, relevant pre- and in-service teacher development to enhance continuous teacher preparation and professional growth was badly needed, especially in the Zimbabwean context. It emerged from the LFGD that the students' learning needs and their environment, let alone the curriculum, are ever-changing, hence the need for continuous teacher preparation and professional development to capacitate them. Zishiri et.al (2024) discovered that the growing demand for novel teaching approaches, personalised learning experiences, and interactive digital platforms that are heritage-based, practical, and result-oriented necessitated the assistance of a skilled educator as well as necessary technological resources. From the RRL, Zishiri et al. (2024) also observed that, "Without adequate technological resources, institutions were struggling to incorporate innovative teaching methods, personalised learning experiences and interactive digital platforms which are fundamental aspects of Education 5.0."

RIHubs and ICT Utilisation and Access

The need for mastery and use of digital platforms in RIHubs in HEIs was identified as a key issue by the LFGD. Nevertheless, they observed that lack of ICT culture in teachers' colleges was hindering the development of RIHubs in TE in Zimbabwe. It also emerged from the Review of related Literature (RRL) and QDA that teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe generally lacked the ICT and entrepreneurial culture for them to fully embrace the RIHubs as mandatory teaching and learning centres of necessity, in the context of the HBE 5.0 philosophy (Garwe, 2018; Chigora & Zvavahera, 2022; Zishiri et al., 2024). The SFGD agreed that ICT literacy was emphasised and quite evident in their studies, but bemoaned the lack of application in research, innovation and business incubation.

Challenges in Embracing RIHubs in Teachers' Colleges

It emerged from SFGD that there were challenges in adopting RIHubs as teaching/learning centres of choice in TE. The Science and Engineering student teachers described their labs as deplorable. KI1 in Case C reported that the engineering workshops were outdated, and it was observed that there was obsolete equipment therein. From observation (OBS), these workstations badly needed retooling, to say the least. To the lecturer respondent (KI3 in Case A), a state-of-the-art RIHub was a pipe dream at their institution because

of lack of resources like relevant infrastructure. They revealed that teachers' colleges were relying on industry to expose their student teachers to modern equipment and systems during work-integrated learning programmes (WILP). However, it was observed from LFGD that industry in Zimbabwe, especially in rural communities, was also lagging far behind in modern technology advancement.

KI1 in Case C, in concurrence with KI3 in Case A, identified a lack of funding as a major setback in developing RIHubs in TE institutions. They bemoaned the lack of a budget for the construction and retooling of RIHubs in teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe. The RRL also identified funding as a critical impediment to the creation of RIHubs in HEIs. In Table 1, Khoury et al. (2024) identified inefficient funding distribution in research, development, and innovation (RDI) fields as a major concern in this regard. From these observations, funding seems to be the major stumbling block which negatively affects the availability of relevant resources.

The LFGD identified the information gap and lack of expertise including lack of relevant ICT skills and culture as issues hindering the development of RIHubs in HEIs. According to the RRL, Makota et al. (2024) found that there was a lack of relevant and acceptable ICT culture in teacher education in Zimbabwe, despite the newly implemented HBE 5.0 policies. The LFGD also revealed that some lecturers were not well-versed in the needs of the HBE 5.0 policy, while others appeared to be uninformed of what constitutes an ideal RIHub in TE within the context of the HBE 5.0 concept (Mudzengerere, 2024; Zishiri et al., 2024). According to QDA, most teacher colleges lack a culture of research, innovation, and entrepreneurship and this concurs with the ministry's findings (MHTEISTD, 2018). Khoury et al. (2024) noted that culture and mindset were a challenge in colleges, arguing that legacy mindset in academia within HEIs focused on traditional teaching/learning and lacked enough entrepreneurial and risk-taking culture.

Summary

This study employed a qualitative, multiple-case study approach to investigate the development and utilization of Research and Innovation Hubs (RIHubs) in teachers' colleges in Zimbabwe. The discussion focussed on the conceptualisation, contextualisation and practical application of RIHubs in TE. The development and utilisation of RIHubs in teachers' colleges were interrogated. The place of RIHubs in teacher preparation and professional growth was examined and so were the challenges faced by teachers' colleges in embracing RIHubs, as inevitable educational resource centres of necessity in the digital era.

Findings of the Study

The conceptualisation, contextualisation and practical application of RIHubs in TE were found to be in the formative stages of development with some serious gaps therein. It was observed that there were RIHubs policy and practice gaps in various Zimbabwe's teachers' colleges, coupled with the need to realign HBE 5.0 policy with research and innovation practice in these institutions. A big gap was noticed in the access and utilisation of purported RIHubs in teachers' colleges, in that these centres were not fully functional and badly needed relevant equipment (retooling) and competent human capital to serve their purpose. They were found to be a far cry from what was obtaining in universities, despite all teachers' colleges being associate colleges of the University of Zimbabwe. The

resource, knowledge and skills gaps were therefore quite evident in TE despite the great opportunities provided by the Manpower Planning and Development (Amendment) Act (2020) and the HBE 5.0 policy.

Conclusion

The sustainable development and optimum utilisation of RIHubs in TE in Zimbabwe should, all things being equal, ride on the prevailing conducive socio-economic and political teacher development environment, as prescribed by the Manpower Planning and Development Amendment Act 2020, and the HBE 5.0 Policy. There is, arguably, great potential, in the Zimbabwean context, for teachers' colleges to put up vibrant RIHubs if relevant financial, material and human capital resources can be mobilised for that purpose. TESC and Teachers' colleges need to have a RIHubs Policy to guide the development and utilisation of these resource centres. It can, therefore, be concluded that the construction and effective utilisation of RIHubs and MOOCs, in TE, is key to the realisation of HBE 5.0 philosophy, NDS1 and 2 and subsequently, sustainable socio-economic development in Zimbabwe.

Recommendations

- The Zimbabwean government and stakeholders, including HEIs, TESC, and MHTEISTD, should prioritise developing a national policy on intellectual property, research, and innovation, with a focus on RIHubs in HEIs, especially teachers' colleges.
- The government should allocate at least 3% of its GDP on R&D. This financing should be expanded to encompass commercialisation and the development of research and innovation hubs in TE, ensuring that entrepreneurs have enough office space and RIHubs for prototype development and testing. HEIs should also develop other infrastructure, such as affordable internet and solar power.
- HEIs should provide 10% of their income to research, innovation, and industrialisation efforts, including the establishment of RIHubs in teacher colleges and polytechnics.
- The government and financial sector should offer financial support to young innovators and entrepreneurs without collateral.
- The government and higher education institutions should simplify the procedure of obtaining seed funding for research and innovation projects.
- The whole education system should introduce courses that encourage research, innovation and entrepreneurship early enough. The ICT and indeed all other curriculum should be re-aligned to the HBE 5.0 Philosophy to enhance the development of innovative and creative students and teachers.
- Teacher development programmes for both pre-service student teachers and in-service teachers should make the development and utilisation of RIHubs mandatory in all HEIs, through policy.
- It is also recommended that Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), such as teachers colleges, prioritize the hiring of qualified researcher-innovators who can also lecture. Their instruction should be grounded in practical strategies that lead to tangible outcomes, including laboratory testing, validation of results, and the development of prototypes.
- This study recommends that HTEIs capitalize on favourable conditions within the socio-economic, political, legal, and policy

environments to establish RIHubs and improve their systems. Concurrently, HTEIs must proactively address the challenges that impede the establishment and effective utilization of these hubs.

- Subsequent research is necessary to establish viable and optimal RIHub models tailored to diverse teacher education programmes.
- Further research on Open Virtual Mobility Research and Innovation Hubs in teacher education is strongly recommended.
- We recommend that researchers pursue the gaps both substantive and emerging that this study has uncovered in the field of RIHubs.

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